

“Resettled” Musical Practices of the Nharo from D’kar (Botswana)

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Abstract

This article investigates group and individual musical practices of Nharo musicians and composers from D’kar, a village situated in western Botswana, 40 Km east of Ghanzi. Nowadays, about 2,000 Nharo (or Naro) speaking people live in D’kar. Nharo is a Khoisan language spoken in eastern Namibia, too. Before focusing on the biographies of the music makers and the analysis of some of their compositions on the six-string guitar, the *zhoma* (a four-string adaptation of the pluriarc), and the *danghaderi* (an over one meter long musical bow with external resonator), a brief introduction to the present situation of the Khoisan peoples in Botswana and the history of D’kar Village will be given.

Pratiche musicali “trasferite” dei nharo di D’kar (Botswana). Questo articolo indaga le pratiche musicali di gruppo e individuali di musicisti e compositori nharo del villaggio di D’kar, situato nel Botswana occidentale, 40 Km a est di Ghanzi. Attualmente a D’kar vivono circa 2.000 persone di lingua nharo (o naro), appartenente al gruppo delle lingue khoisan, parlata anche nella Namibia orientale. Prima di soffermarci sulle biografie dei music makers e sull’analisi di alcune loro composizioni per chitarra a sei corde, zhoma (un adattamento a quattro corde del pluriarco) e danghaderi (un arco musicale lungo oltre un metro con risonatore esterno), verrà presentata la situazione attuale dei khoisan in Botswana e la storia del villaggio di D’kar.

Introduction

According to the British archaeologist John Desmond Clark (1970), the Khoisan inhabited southern Africa for at least 11,000 years, and they are considered the first inhabitants of this part of the continent. The core of their settlement is the Kalahari Desert, a large semi-arid sandy savannah covering most of Botswana, the eastern part of Namibia and some northern

regions of South Africa. The term “Khoisan” was coined by Leonhard Schultze (1928), and then popularized by the anthropologist Isaac Schapera (1930); it is a compound of the terms “khoi” and “san”. In different Khoe languages, such as Nama and Korana, the term “khoi” means “people”, whereas the term “san” means “hunter-gatherer”, “bushman” (Barnard 1992, Suzman 2017). According to the anthropologist Alan Barnard:

The Khoisan peoples are a large cluster of southern African nations. Some of them are pastoralists, others are hunter-gatherers or hunter-gatherer-fishermen, and virtually all today include individuals who work as herds-men or labourers for members of other ethnic groups. Yet, in spite of differences associated with their subsistence pursuits, many otherwise diverse Khoisan peoples share a great number of common features of territorial organization, gender relations, kinship, ritual, and cosmology. These features are not randomly distributed; nor have they simply diffused from one group to another as single culture traits. They represent elements of structures held in common across economic, cultural, linguistic, and ‘racial’ boundaries. (Barnard 1992: 3)

Khoisan peoples are also known in Botswana under the term *Basarwa* which literally means “people who do not breed cattle”. It is a Setswana term which is considered pejorative by most Khoisan speakers (Suzman 2017). Setswana is a Bantu language spoken by Tswana, the main ethno-linguistic group in the country. This language is the most spoken in Botswana, but English is also widely spoken as the country was a British protectorate from 1885 to 1966. In the past and also today, Khoisan peoples have been labelled with different terms most of them derogatory, e.g. “hottentot” is an onomatopoeia which refers to the click consonants of Khoisan languages (Suzman 2017: XII). Nowadays, the community who lives in D’kar identifies itself as Khoisan, more precisely as Nharo which is also the language they speak. Nharo (or Naro) is a dialect of the Tshu-Kwe, a Khoe-Kwadi language spoken in eastern Namibia, too (see Appendix).

Today, around 65,000 Khoisan live in Botswana (Hitchcock, Sapignoli 2019), which is the country with the highest number of Khoisan people in Africa; others live in Namibia, South Africa, Angola and Zimbabwe. Established in 1961, the Central Kalahari Game Reserve (CKGR) is the second largest game reserve in the world. It was the “home” of Khoisan peoples who used to move freely inside of it, hunting wild animals and gathering. The CKGR was established in order to protect the Kalahari ecosystem and the life of the Khoisan (Suzman 2002). After Botswana gained independence in 1966, the new government intended «to develop the country economically partly by shifting from the traditional communal agropastoral system toward an export-oriented private system of meat and mineral production» (Bisele *et al.*, 1989: 112). In this perspective, in 1974, the government started the Bushmen Development Programme, then in 1978 renamed Remote Area Development Programme (RADP): «the RADP encouraged the remote area dwellers, known as RADs, the majority of whom were San, to relocate to government-planned settlements with a water supply, schools, clinics, and income-generating projects» (Pelican, Maruyama 2015: 54).

The resettlement program drastically changed the way of life of Khoisan people: previously they had depended on hunting and gathering and used to move from one site to another in bands or band clusters following the changing of seasons, from dry to rainy season in search of water since CKGR has no permanent surface water (Barnard 1992, Suzman 2002). After the resettlement, some accepted the change to resident life, seduced by the labour relation with Tswana and white farmers and the permanent supply of water, whereas others moved away from the resettlement sites to the surrounding bushes, forming small bands and hunting, even though it was forbidden by the government that increased also the number of ranger patrols in the CKGR (Tanaka 1987, Pelican, Maruyama 2015).

Relocations were voluntary, but in 1996 the government of Botswana exacerbated the resettlement program especially towards the Xade Village in the western part of the CKGR. The London based NGO Survival International therefore started a campaign against the Botswana government claiming that it was destroying the Khoisan culture, committing a hate crime against humanity and carrying out ethnic cleansing. According to Survival International, the real reason for the resettlement program was linked to the diamond industry, since some International companies, such as De Beers, had an exploration concession in the CKGR granted by the Botswana government (Suzman 2002). More than twenty resettlement projects involving the Khoisan peoples have been conducted also in Namibia, of which Skoonheid is the best-known (Suzman 2017).

D'kar and the Ghanzi District

D'kar is situated 40 Km east of Ghanzi, the administrative centre of the Ghanzi District in western Botswana, bordering Namibia to the west and extending towards the east into the Central Kalahari Game Reserve. This area was previously inhabited by several thousand Khoisan peoples of the Nharo, !Kung and G/wi linguistic groups. In the early 1890s, Cecil Rhodes decided to settle a colony of Afrikaner ranchers in the western part of the former British Protectorate of Bechuanaland in order to contain the eastward expansion from German south-west Africa. Between 1895 and 1899, about fifty Afrikaner families settled on the territory around Ghanzi after the British Colonial office declared the area to be Crown Land in 1884; no land negotiations were conducted with the Khoisan peoples and the relations with the first settlers were harmonious (Barnard 1980b, Bisele *et al.*, 1989, Guenther 1979, Marshall Thomas 1989).

Unfortunately, the situation drastically changed after the Second World War:

Until 1933 the Ghanzi Block was largely unfarmed and large stretches of open veld lay between the few Afrikaner outposts on which game continued to graze and San continued to hunt. Thus, in the first three decades of settlement, the San had little or no feeling of being displaced. During these years the lifestyle of some of the White farmers was little different from their San or African neighbours: some Whites, for example, lived in wat-

tle-and-daub huts. The early settlers were poor and had to augment their supplies with morama beans which San labourers collected and which were stored and used throughout the year for their own tables. [...]

After the Second World War, and especially in the 1960s, the older generation of paternalistic settlers gave way to an increasingly profit-oriented type of businessman farmer producing beef for the export market. [...] The cattle post received a constant stream of visitors from hunting and gathering groups living on the periphery of the farms and from further afield. [...] The cattle workers exchanged their labour for the means of survival, wages, the San population of the Ghanzi District underwent a process of proletarianization. [...] In the 1960s a number of the farms changed hands. As old people retired to the towns, white businessmen, mostly English, bought up the farms and set about running them more “efficiently”. [...] Since they had no ties of sentiment to the San, they fired dozens of wage workers and drove hundreds of hangers-on off their land. The dispossession of the San had been implicit in their living situation since 1900, but the full weight of their loss did not strike them until full-fledged capitalist ranching came into their midst. (Bisele *et al.*, 1989: 127-128)

Today, feelings of frustration, alienation and discontent fill the hearts of the Khoisan peoples who live in the Ghanzi area. Most of them suffer from hunger and disease. Alcoholism is a very bad plague, especially among the younger generations that cannot compete against Bantu-speaking people (Tswana and Herero) in search of a gratifying job mainly due to the process of modernization of technologies. Unemployment is a very big problem, too. So, in the area around the city of Ghanzi, a large number of Khoisan peoples became squatters on the land that their ancestors had occupied for thousands of years before the arrival of Afrikaners and Bantu-speaking people. These problems were already noticed by the anthropologist Mathias G. Guenther who conducted an extensive fieldwork in the Ghanzi area in the 1970s (Guenther 1975a, 1975b, 1976, 1979).

D’kar is the village where I conducted my field research thanks to the invaluable help provided by the interpreter and informant Alfred Cg’ase Tshumu, a native Nharo speaker, and my wife Silvia Montaquila, whose photographs are published in this article.¹ Today, D’kar is inhabited by about 2,000 Nharo speaking people; all the musicians described in this article speak Nharo. In D’kar there are also a few Afrikaners, Tswana and Herero people.

The first anthropologist who published a monograph devoted to a single Khoisan people was Dorothea Bleek. In 1928 she published *The Naron. A Bushman Tribe of the Central Kalahari*. Her book focuses on the key aspects of the way of life of a Nharo tribe which was settled in Sandfontein (Namibia). Nowadays, in Botswana, the Nharo live mainly in the western part of the Ghanzi District. The area around Ghanzi and D’kar is rich in water resources, and that is why they used to spend long periods at large permanent waterholes. They used to live in bands (*tsou-ba* in Nharo language) or band clusters of three to twenty huts, moving freely throughout their territory according to

¹ I had the possibility to conduct my field research in Botswana in 2018 and 2019 thanks to the three-year project (2018-2020) *Biographies and work analyses of East/Central African composers* (P 30718-G26) coordinated by Gerhard Kubik and financed by the Austrian Science Fund (FWF).

FIGURE 1. Some members of the D'caro group sitting in front of an outdoor kitchen (D'kar, 12th July 2019; photo S. Montaquila).

the availability of plants and animals: «more recently, with the acquisition of goats and the greater dependence on the ranchers for their livelihood, Nharo have tended to stay closer to permanent sources of water» (Barnard 1992: 139).²

In 1965, the Gereformeerde Kerk, a branch of South Africa's Dutch Reformed Church, established a mission station and farm in D'kar: «about 100 Khoisan, mostly Nharo and !Kung, were settled and given instructions in agricultural and pastoral techniques, along with Christian teaching» (Bisele *et al.*, 1989: 130). Around the permanent supplies of water provided by the Gereformeerde Kerk's mission, a settlement of Nharo started growing. In recent times, the area was donated to the Nharo people and nowadays the board of the church is made up of Nharo. As I could see during my field research, most of the Nharo identify themselves as Christians, even though they do not usually attend the mass. Dutch Reformed Church has set up mission stations also in Namibia, such as the one in Tsumkwe very close to the north-east border of Botswana.

Since D'kar is a private farm belonging to the San Reformed Church, it does not receive government funding, so the D'kar based NGO Kuru Development Trust assists

² For further details, the anthropologist Alan Barnard published studies regarding Nharo kinship (1978), ritual (1979), gender (1980a), settlement patterns (1980b) and cosmology (1980c). Furthermore, the anthropologist Mathias Georg Guenther produced a large number of studies regarding the Khoisan peoples in the Ghanzi District (1975a, 1976, 1979), Nharo religion (1975b, 1981) and a significant monography regarding the Nharo people (1986).

Khoisan peoples «to develop sustainable livelihoods through education, training, art and community mobilization. Amongst other things, the Kuru Development Trust mobilizes the youth, local women, and the elderly to undertake community projects, support health services to the community and develop San leadership to guide the village, and the community into the future» (Chawawa 2015: 131).

The Kuru Art Project founded in 1990 and situated in D'kar, is a project of the Kuru Development Trust. It encourages and assists more than forty Khoisan artists by showing them art materials and teaching them techniques, as well as taking care of the administration and marketing of their art. Inside the building in D'kar, a permanent exhibition of paintings made by Khoisan people is set up.³ Furthermore, Dqae Qare San Lodge, another important project financed by the Kuru Development Trust, is entirely managed by D'kar residents who welcome guests, prepare meals and rooms and offer extra activities, such as bush walks, traditional dances, fire making, craft making and storytelling. Dqae Qare San Lodge was created in 1993 thanks to the support of the Dutch Government (Directorate-General for International Cooperation) and the Netherlands Development Organisation (SNV).⁴

Xhara Qoma

Xhara Qoma is one of the most talented musicians in D'kar. He was born in 1952 in the bushes outside the village. In the past, he used to move freely together with his band in search of veld food and water. He was also a skilled hunter. In 1997, Xhara decided to settle in D'kar together with his wife and eight children (four boys and four girls) because of the Botswana Remote Area Development Programme. He had to change drastically his way of life, from nomadic to residing: Xhara mainly decided to do it in order to give his children a better future, including a school education and health assistance.

On 12th July 2019 he said to me:

Nowadays, life is tough for us here. Before 1997, I used to hunt and gather, I did not need money to buy food. If I was hungry, I could move freely in search of food. Now I cannot do it because hunting is forbidden by the government, furthermore the land is not ours, it belongs to the government and to the farmers. Even if I want to visit a friend of mine who works at a private farm, I have to ask for the land owner's permission. Nowadays, I have to buy food with money, it is very hard since I do not have a steady job. Sometimes I perform for tourists or at traditional events with the *setinkane* (see Fig. 3) or the guitar at Dqae Qare San Lodge, but it is not enough. I am not happy with this modern life, I would like to cast a spell and come back to "traditional life" to show to the younger generations how beautiful hunting and gathering was, how tasty it was

³ For further information: <<http://www.kuruart.com/>> (last access: 31st May 2022).

⁴ For further information: <<https://www.dqae.org/>> (last access: 31st May 2022).

FIGURE 2. Xhara Qoma (D'kar, 12th July 2019; photo S. Montaquila).

to eat springbok's meat and drink the juice of the roots. Unfortunately, I do not have a land of my own where I can do all these activities. Nowadays, the younger generations do not know how to track, how to dig a root or how to play traditional instruments. The culture is dying.⁵

Xhara Qoma is also a *tsho khwe*, literally a "medicine man", because in Nharo language *tsho* means "medicine" and *khwe* means "person". He says that he can feel when somebody is not in good health, so he usually conducts a traditional dance at night around a fire with songs and hand-clapping to heal the people. In the past, medicine men and women were the doctors of the community, as Dorothea Francis Bleek wrote in her book about the Nharo (1928: 28). Sometimes, Xhara plays also the *setinkane* during the night dance that may last six to eight hours. Medicine dances are common among all Khoisan peoples (Barnard 1979, Guenther 1975b, 1999, Marshall Thomas 1989). Nharo medicine men «claim that the evil they remove from the bodies of those present at the dance either is thrown to spirits outside the dance circle, or, unusually, is dissipated through the body of the medicine man, who himself is voluntarily possessed by a spirit» (Barnard 1992: 153).

⁵ I have collected all the statements in Nharo language by Xhara Qoma cited in this paragraph on 12th July 2019 in D'kar. Alfred Cg'ase Tshumu translated them into English.

FIGURE 3. Xhara Qoma playing his *setinkane* lamellophone. The instrument is played also by Tswana people. A metal can is used as resonator, in fact the term *setinkane* is a local corruption of the English terms “sitting” and “can”. In Nharo language the instrument is also named *dengo* (D’kar, 12th July 2019; photo S. Montaquila).⁶

Traditional medicine dances are rather frequent, at least one per month or sometimes more frequently, for example when a member of the community is gravely ill.⁷

Over the past years, Xhara Qoma has participated in President’s Day Competition playing both the *setinkane* and the six-string guitar. He has also achieved the second position at regional level in the Ghanzi District. Held every year, the aim of the President’s Day Competition is to promote and support local artists and craftsmen with rich cash prizes. Organized by the Ministry of Youth, Sports and Culture to promote Botswana talents, the competition includes a regional preliminary level and a grand final in Gaborone. The categories are: Traditional Songs and Dances, Contemporary Music, Choral Music, Traditional Instruments and Visual Arts and Crafts. In 2018, Xhara Qoma took up visual art and was also accepted as an artist in the Kuru Art Project.

⁶ Historical recordings of songs with *setinkane* are contained in the following LPs: *The Music of !Kung Bushmen of the Kalahari Desert, Africa* (1962) with recordings made by John Phillipson (tracks A1, A2, A3, A4, B1 and B2); *Instrumental Music of the Kalahari San* (1982) with three recordings made by Marjorie Shostak (track A6), Megan Biesele (track B3) and Nicholas England (track B4); and *Traditional Music of Botswana, Africa* (1983) with three recordings made by Elizabeth Nelbach Wood in the village of Kang (tracks B10, 11 and 12).

⁷ The LP *Healing Dance Music of the Kalahari San* (1982) contains healing dance music recorded among the !Kung San by Richard Katz, Megan Biesele and Marjorie Shostack between 1968 and 1972 in the north-west of the Kalahari Desert (Botswana).

FIGURE 4. Xhara Qoma playing his acoustic guitar (D'kar, 12th July 2019; photo S. Montaquila).

Xhara plays a six-string Tanglewood TWRT Roadster acoustic guitar which is a gift from a friend of his (Fig. 4). When he was a young boy, he used to play a home-made guitar: the instrument was built using an oilcan as a resonance box inside which the carved wooden keyboard was inserted and the strings were fixed. These home-made instruments were called *motontonyane* or *senara* in Setswana language. It is interesting to note that the shape and the way of making the instrument are identical to those of four-string home-made banjos “type A” described by Gerhard Kubik (2017: 123-125).

Furthermore, in southern Africa, particularly in the areas inhabited by South African Zulu, Khoisan and Tswana, a three- or four-string lute-shaped chordophone named *ramkie* was common from the early 18th century. This chordophone was a local adaptation of the Portuguese *rabequinha* or *cavaquinho*, which was introduced into South Africa thanks to European sailors (for further information see Coplan 2008, Kaemmer 2008, Kaye 2008, Kirby 2013, Kubik 2017).

Xhara Qoma does not play the four-string guitar, which is the instrument played by the Tswana people. Tswana guitarists become one-man bands when they play four-string guitar, thanks to the continuous interlocking game between the bass string (the fourth) and the melodies played on the three high strings (for further details see Sreetsi 2013, Cosentino 2019b, 2022). Xhara said to me: «four-string is not my style, I play the guitar in a different way. I play six-string guitar which is the San way. I play it exclusively

by fretting the strings with my left hand from below the keyboard while most Tswana guitarists do it from above».

Analysis of the song *Koli* by Xhara Qoma

On 12th July 2019, I documented three songs played by Xhara Qoma in D'kar Village: *Haa na ta qoo* (Let's go), a song of his own composition about nomadic life played on a *setinkane*; *Sunkuri* (Dream), an instrumental guitar song, and *Koli*, a song played on a guitar. *Koli* is the name of a dance performed by Nharo people, the instrumental part of the song is "traditional" while both the vocal melody and the lyrics were composed by Xhara Qoma ([Video 1](#)). Below the lyrics in Nharo with translation:⁸

Koli

Iye iye uwe iye uwe khasa
Koe nxae, koe nxae ghe oh eh
Cui ra, cuise, khasa
Khoe xaoe haa xae qoo xaesa kuru na

Koli

Iye iye uwe iye uwe I am a giver
 I say this, I say this ghe oh eh
 I am alone, just me, I am a giver
 Come let's get together and be one

As the musical transcription reveals (Musical example 1), *Koli* can be divided into cycles of 12 elementary pulses, which is the number placed at the beginning of each stave. In sub-Saharan African music, elementary pulses are the smallest time-units between the actions of the musicians and the performers. The elementary pulse-line is isomorphous and unaccented and it is graphically represented by Gerhard Kubik with a grid to transcribe African music. The elementary pulse-line can be totally silent and merely present as a subjective awareness shared by all participants during the performance. This elementary pulse-line is divided into cycles marked by formula numbers, these cycles are melodic-harmonic segments constantly repeated throughout the songs (for further details see Kubik 1983, 1999: chapter 3, 2010, vol. 2: chapter 6).

Xhara Qoma tunes the guitar with the following sequence: C \sharp_4 – A \sharp_4 – F \sharp_3 – C \sharp_3 – B $_3$ – E $_2$ (from the first to the sixth), the hand-made capo is set at the second fret so the sequence is one tone higher: D \sharp_4 – C $_4$ – G \sharp_3 – D \sharp_3 – C \sharp_3 – F \sharp_2 . This tuning is very different from the European standard one (E $_4$ – B $_3$ – G $_3$ – D $_3$ – A $_2$ – E $_2$), and it proves the individual creativity of African guitarists in conceiving personal tuning, just like the ones documented by Gerhard Kubik (1995), John Low (1982) and myself (Cosentino 2019a, 2019b, 2019c).

Koli is in the key of C \sharp major and the guitar part is based on the I, IV and V chords. The song can be divided into cycles of 12 elementary pulses as you can see in the Musical example 1, which is transcribed one semitone down. Each chord is kept for four ele-

⁸ Alfred Cg'ase Tshumu transcribed the Nharo lyrics of *Koli* and *Xgoe* by Xhoxhae Xhukuri (see below) and translated them into English.

mentary pulses (4 + 4 + 4). What is very interesting to highlight is the rhythmic pattern played on the guitar by Xara Qoma using the thumb of the right hand: he plays the chords alternating an upward and downward movement of the right hand ([Video 1](#)), in the acoustic guitar section of the Musical example 1, the upward (▲) and downward (▼) movements are indicated with a black triangle. So, the rhythmic structure of the song can be represented as follows:

(12) ▼ · ▼ · ▼ ▲ ▼ · ▼ · ▼ ▲

As you can see in the Musical example 1, the first cycle of 12 elementary pulses of the vocal melody is characterised by a yodel technique: a very rapid change from chest register to head register (*falsetto*) on the syllables “iye” and “uwe”. What is very interesting to specify is that Xhara Qoma improvises vocal melodies with the syllables “iye” and “uwe” during the medicine dances too.

Xhoxhae Xhukuri

Xhoxhae Xhukuri was born in 1963 in the bushes around D’kar. She settled in D’kar Village as a young woman with one child, today she has ten children and still lives in D’kar. She plays the *zhoma*, a four-string instrument that could be a recent adaptation of the pluriarc *≠goukhas* played by Damara people from Namibia and !Kung people (Kirby 2013: 326-328). The *≠goukhas* described by Percival R. Kirby has a wooden resonator and five strings tuned with different notes. The musician plays it seated, placing the instrument on the ground in front of him and plucking the strings with his fingers. As described by Kirby, a *≠goukhas* player hums without uttering any words while playing, it is a very intimate instrument, played mainly for the pleasure it gives; Kirby also tells of a blind musician who started crying while playing it. On 12th July 2019, I documented the same deep emotional state when Xhoxhae Xhukuri dried her tears between one song and another. Elizabeth Marshall Thomas (1989: 219-221) documented the same instrument among the !Kung in Botswana, it was named *guashi* and was played by a young man who composed different songs. In her article (1976), Elizabeth Nelbach Wood describes also a four (or even five) string pluriarc with a wooden resonator named *guashi*.

In the *Instrumental Music of the Kalahari San* LP (1982) there are four songs with the pluriarc played by !Kung people and recorded by Nicholas England in northeast Namibia (1951-1955) and Megan Biesele in northwest Botswana (1972). The ones recorded by England are accompanied by a wooden resonator pluriarc with five gut strings, the first one with three men’s voices (track A1) and the second one with one man’s voice (track B5), while the songs recorded by Biesele are accompanied by a pluriarc, whose resonance box was an oilcan; both songs are sung by a woman named Hwan//a (tracks A2 and B6). Unfortunately, neither England nor Biesele documented the vernacular names of the instruments.

FIGURE 5. Xhoxhae Xhukuri's *zhoma*. Particular of the wooden tuning pegs (D'kar, 12th July 2019; photo S. Montaquila).

On 1st September 1992, Gerhard Kubik and Moya A. Malamusi recorded 15 Km from Bagani (north-eastern Namibia) a five-string pluriarc with a wood resonator named *gauka* played by a Mbarakwengo speaking musician named Kamate Johannes (Kubik 1994: Fig. 7). After showing them my videorecording of the song *Xgoe* by Xhoxhae Xhukuri ([Video 2](#)), Kubik and Malamusi reminded me also of a !Kung speaking woman named Dena Pikenien that they recorded in Gobabis (eastern Namibia) on 25th November 1991. Sitting under a tree, she played a six-string pluriarc named *too* whose resonance box was not made of wood but was an oilcan. She plucked the strings with the thumb and index of the right hand and the thumb of the left hand.⁹ Kubik says that the *too* is an important string instrument in south-western Angola, and in 1965 he documented some specimens with wooden resonators too.¹⁰

Just like the *too* played by Dena Pikenien, also the *zhoma* (or *goroshi*) documented by John Brearley in August 1982 among the Makaukau living near Ghanzi had an oilcan as a resonator (Brearley 1984: 56). The name of the instrument is the same as the one played by Xhoxhae Xhukuri, even though it shows a new organological development: a short wooden neck is inserted into the oilcan resonator, and the string bearer no longer follows the principle of the pluriarc, but seems to be inspired by the above mentioned

⁹ Film No. 6 (1991) Private Archives Kubik/Malamusi, Vienna.

¹⁰ Private communication (18th October 2020).

FIGURE 6. Xhoxhae Xhukuri playing her *zhoma* (D'kar, 12th July 2019; photo S. Montaquila).

home-made guitars (*motontonyane*), *ramkie* and the home-made banjo “type A” with vertical home-made wooden tuning pegs (Fig. 5). Furthermore, the upper side of the resonance box has two f-holes in the middle. Just like the musicians described above, Xhoxhae plays the *zhoma* sitting on the ground, placing the instrument in front of her (Fig. 6). The *zhoma* she plays is a gift from the San Cultural Museum in D'kar, because she lost her own instrument. Just like Xhara Qoma, Xhoxhae can play also the *setinkane*.

Regarding her musical activities she said to me:

When I sing and play the *zhoma*, I can feel a special excitement, I feel like my body is burning, my heart starts pumping faster and sometimes I start crying. The songs that I play lead me into an altered state of consciousness. The *zhoma* is for me like a medicine, a traditional healing. *Zhoma* is my life, I play it when I feel down, just to motivate and elevate my mood. I also make a living with it. The songs that I sing reflect my life, without music I have no life. I know I have a special gift to feel such emotions, I have received it from my grandparents, they played the *zhoma*, too. I did not go to school, I grew up around my grandparents and my parents. I learned playing the *zhoma* looking at them, learning all the instrumental tricks and how to sing, too. Today I try to teach my children the *zhoma* because it is something very special and I have to pass it on. ¹¹

¹¹ I have collected all the statements in Nharo language by Xhoxhae Xhukuri cited in this paragraph on 14th July 2019 in D'kar. Alfred Cg'ase Tshumu translated them into English.

Regarding the economic side of her profession, Xhoxhae pointed out that «music has improved my spiritual life, unfortunately not my economic situation. I do not get much money when I perform live even if the cultural events are sponsored by the government. You know, life is hard but I have no choice, because music chose me». About her life before the settlement in D'kar Village, she said to me: «life in the bush was amazing, but it was hard because water was a challenge and we used to squeeze water from the roots or drink the juice of *tsama* melons.¹² Today life is very different and it is very hard, too, because it is a life of money».

Xhoxhae Xhukuri is also an artist of the Kuru Art Project where she learned how to paint on cloth. In later years, she also started to embroider on the painted cloths with tiny stitches. In 2018, thanks to this artistic technique, she won a first prize in the President's Day Competition at regional preliminary level for Crafts category. In 2010, she was also invited by the local artistic director of the Competition to play the *zhoma* during the event.

Analysis of the song *Xgoe* by Xhoxhae Xhukuri

On 12th July 2019, I documented two songs with *zhoma* composed and played by Xhoxhae Xhukuri in D'kar Village. On that occasion, she wore her “traditional stage clothes” made of springbok skin together with some coloured necklaces and a hand-made yellow and orange headband and a green and orange belt. These ornaments are a new development of the ostrich eggshell beads hand-made by the Nharo people and described by Dorothea Frances Bleek (1928: 9-10). Xhoxhae uses this outfit when she plays at traditional events or for tourists at lodges. The compositions that I documented were *Tcibi* (The laughing dove), a song about a baby whose crying was calmed down by the sound of a laughing dove, and *Xgoe*, which is a Nharo word used to denote a traditional dance. *Xgoe* is about Xhoxhae's struggle in modern life and her feeling of frustration and alienation because things are not moving the way she wants ([Video 2](#)). Below the lyrics in Nharo language with translation:

Xgoe

Aiye Aiye

Tii ra cui ra, aresa e

Khoe tuue, khoe tuue

Tii ra cgomga ra, aresa e

Xgoe

Aiye Aiye

I am alone, it is such a pity for me

People, people

I am very sad, it is such a pity for me

¹² *Tsama* melons can be found all over the Kalahari Desert. Especially in autumn; they provide the only liquid available for all the Khoisan in the desert (Marshall Thomas 1989, Barnard 1992, Suzman 2017). It looks like a watermelon and it is very watery in texture. Shot in 1955 and then published in 1971, *Bitter Melons* by John Marshall focuses on a small band of /Gwi Khoisan living in the Central Kalahari Desert. At the very beginning of the film, you can watch the entire process of first gathering and then drinking the juice of *tsama* melons after having mashed the pulp inside.

<i>Are da ko are da ko</i>	I wonder and I wonder
<i>Tii ra cui ra, aresa e</i>	I am alone, it is such a pity for me
<i>Setae setae</i>	I struggle and I struggle
<i>Tii ra cui ra, aresa e</i>	I am alone, it is such a pity for me
<i>Ii ko nxae aiye ii ko nxae aiye</i>	I say and I say
<i>Tii ra cui ra, aresa e</i>	I am alone, it is such a pity for me

Xhoxhae tunes the *zhoma* with the following sequence: $A_{b_4} - D_4 - B_{b_3} - F_4$ (from left to right). The fundamental measures 231 Hz (B_{b_3} , -16 cents) and the other strings correspond to the fifth, sixth and seventh natural harmonics over the fundamental: $D_4 = 291$ Hz an interval of 400 cents (a major third); $F_4 = 356$ Hz an interval of 748 cents (a perfect fifth, +48 cents); $A_{b_4} = 408$ Hz an interval of 985 cents (a minor seventh, -15 cents).¹³ As revealed by the Musical example 2, both the vocal and *zhoma* melodic lines emerge from this tetratonic scale derived from the harmonic series over one fundamental.¹⁴

Xhoxhae plays the four strings of the *zhoma* with the thumb and the index of both hands: A_{b_4} with the index of the left hand, D_4 using the thumb of the left hand, B_{b_3} with the thumb of the right hand, and F_4 with the index of the right hand. This motional pattern is very structured and the musician always plays a string using the same finger ([Video 2](#)). It is important to consider that in sub-Saharan Africa this instrumental technique (thumb-index) is also used for playing different musical instruments, such as the *bangwe* zither from Malawi (Kubik 2010, vol. 2: 213-215, Malamusi 2019) and in finger-style guitar technique (Low 1982, Kubik 1995, Cosentino 2019a, 2019c), just to cite some of them.

Xgoe can be divided into cycles of 12 elementary pulses (Musical example 2). The *zhoma* part played by Xhoxhae always has the same rhythmic structure: the 7-note pattern into a 12 elementary pulse cycle characterising the song which can be represented as follows:

(12) X X · X · X · X · X X ·

The whole melody of the *zhoma* part is made up of four cycles of 12 elementary pulses, this part is repeated in an almost identical way with very few variations throughout the song. Regarding the voice, it rhythmically overlaps with the *zhoma* part, and it is made up of the same four notes of the instrument even if the melodic line is different. Just like *Koli* by Xhara Qoma, the vocal melody of *Xgoe* is characterised by a yodel technique on the syllables “aye”, “iye” and “uwe”; these melodies are always improvised by Xhoxhae throughout the song (see [Video 2](#)).

¹³ The fundamental frequencies of each string have been measured with S_TOOLS-STx signal processing application developed by the Acoustic Research Institute of the Austrian Academy of Sciences. The frequencies must be considered to be the well approximated average (about ± 1 Hz).

¹⁴ For further in-depth analyses regarding harmonics-based systems in Africa see Kubik 1985, 2010, vol. I: chapter 3, section 2).

FIGURE 7. On the left side Xhoxhae Xhukuri holds in her right hand her *zhoma*. Proceeding to the right some members of the Dcaro group: Kgakgam Kaase holding in her right hand the *danghaderi*, Namaçgae Kaase, Tabaxae Kaase, Nconxae Xgaiga, Qose Qarega, Khoabaxae Thogo and Xaga Tcuixgao (D'kar, 12th July 2019; photo S. Montaquila).

Dcaro group

Dcaro is a musical group exclusively composed of women based in D'kar Village. “Dcaro” is a Nharo word which means “ostrich”. They play an over one meter long musical bow named *danghaderi* (or *takadiri*) which is an onomatopoeic word. Today, the members of the Dcaro group play this musical bow both to entertain themselves and to make their living at cultural events sponsored by the government or for the tourists at Dqae Qare San Lodge (Fig. 7). In the past, the *danghaderi* was played exclusively by women «when the hunters were far away, to bring them good luck and to celebrate when they came back with meat. Today life is different, it is more complicated because hunting is forbidden by the government», as Qose Qarega (Fig. 11), the leader of the group, said to me in an interview.¹⁵

The instrument was documented by John Brearley among the Nharo in the Ghanzi District in August 1982:

A very different way of playing the bow was also in evidence, using an enamelled basin as a resonator. This is known by the Nharo Bushmen as the *!am !goma, !goma n!are*, (“Foot-

¹⁵ I have collected all the statements in Nharo language made by Qose Qarega cited in this paragraph, D'kar on 14th July 2019. Alfred Cg'ase Tshumu translated them into English.

bow”), or *Tandiri* [...]. The Makaukau call it *Dakateri* – possibly a corruption of “Doctor”, but how this name came about I was not able to discover. The instrument was only played by women. A basin was placed upside down over a shallow hollow in the sand, and the principal player sat on the ground, her left foot tucked underneath her, with a long bow (about 5 feet in length) resting on her left knee about 12 inches from the end of the stick, and the other end of the bow resting on the basin, which was to her right. Her right foot pressed on the stick of the bow roughly in the middle, keeping it in fairly firm contact with the basin. Her left hand held a metal tobacco pipe which stopped the string at the required point, roughly where the left knee was, in this case. [...] Her right hand held a thin stick as did her two assistants, and between the three of them they created a composite rhythm; nothing very intricate, and extremely repetitious. No harmonics were heard; the only notes discernible were the sound of the unstopped string, a stopped note (usually a major sixth above open string), and an additional rather faint note one fifth above the stopped note. This third sound is produced from the shorter length of the string when stopped. The “tunes” (if they can really be counted as such) mainly represent animals and their gaits, but I heard one which was intended to describe a courtship. (Brearley 1984: 51-52)

The members of the Dcaro group play the *danghaderi* in a circle sitting on the ground with a very structured and complex interlocking game, striking the metallic string tightened to the wooden bow at both ends. Each member of the group holds in her hands a thin wooden stick (Fig. 8). Only one member of the group holds the central wooden part of the instrument down to the ground with her right knee and changes the pitch of the *danghaderi* using a metallic slider, just like the one described by John Brearley (Fig. 9). One of the two wooden ends of the bow is placed on an upside-down concave metallic dish on the ground that works as a resonance box. Furthermore, one member of the group slightly lifts up and releases one side of the metallic dish to the ground; thanks to this movement the musician changes the harmonic spectrum of the *danghaderi* (Fig. 10). The wooden part of the instrument is made of *xane* (*Grewia flava*).

The *danghaderi* can be compared with the monoidiochord zithers played by Bantu people, such as the *mpeli* recorded by Gerhard Kubik in 1966 in Bigene Village, Nola District, southwestern Central African Republic. The instrument was constructed by two youngsters from a length of raffia leaf stem from which the string was peeled off and raised (two bridges were put underneath). The first performer struck the string using two wooden sticks, while the second performer changed the pitch using a slider. The *mpeli* was laid down on a basin used as a resonator (Kubik 2007: Fig. 6; 2019: Fig. 2).¹⁶ Furthermore, in the 1960s Kubik documented in Angola a group of boys who used a hunting bow putting it on the ground, with string upward, to be struck with sticks. It is significant to point out that the boys had seen this usage of a hunting bow among the !Kung (Kubik 1970).

According to Qose Qarega, in order to achieve a good *danghaderi* performance, the members of the group must be at least five. On 12th July 2019, I documented three songs

¹⁶ Track n. 3 of the attached CD of the Italian edition of Kubik 1999 (Kubik 2007) contains a field recording of the instrument.

FIGURE 8. The Dcaro group. Clockwise from below: Khamxlae Xgaiga, Tabaxae Kaase, Namacgae Kaase, Kgakgam Kaase, Qose Qarega, Xaga Tcuixgao, Khoabaxae Thogo, Qane Qare and Nconxae Xgaiga (D'kar, 12th July 2019; photo S. Montaquila).

FIGURE 9. Namacgae Kaase slightly lifts up and releases one side of the metallic dish to the ground with her left hand. Frame from unpublished video by the author (D'kar, 12th July 2019).

FIGURE 10. Xaga Tcuixgao holds the central wooden part of the instrument down to the ground with her right knee and changes the pitch of the *danghaderi* using a metallic slider. Frame from unpublished video by the author (D'kar, 12th July 2019).

with *danghaderi* performed by the Dcaro group in D'kar. That day the members of the group were nine women: Xaga Tcuixgao, Qose Qarega, Kgakgam Kaase, Namacgae Kaase, Tabaxae Kaase, Khamxlae Xgaiga, Nconxae Xgaiga, Qane Qate, Khoabaxae Tho-

FIGURE 11. Xhoxhae Xhukuri (left) and Qose Qarega (right) sitting in front of Xhoxhae's house made of wood, mud and cow dung (D'kar, 14th July 2019; photo S. Montaquila).

go. They played the following compositions: *Bii* (The horse), *Hagu* (The dog) and *Chobo*, a Nharo term which refers to a special kind of grass of the Kalahari. Just like Xhoxhae Xhukuri, the members of the Dcaro group wore their “traditional stage clothes” made of springbok skin, too, together with some coloured necklaces, belts and headbands in the colours of the Botswana flag (blue, white and black). They use this outfit when they play at traditional events or at tourist lodges.

Qose Qarega was born in 1941 in the bushes around D'kar Village. She conducts the performance of the group with her left hand (see [Video 3](#)), and she teaches the rhythmic patterns and the vocal parts to the other members. She said to me:

I did not go to school so I am not able to read or write. Music is my life, when I perform live, even if the income is not consistent, it is something and I can buy some food. When I was young, life in the bush was wonderful. Our fathers and grandparents were hunters, there was meat for everyone. We also gathered veld food. We used to play the *danghaderi* every day. Today, whenever I play it with my friends, I think about the past because the *danghaderi* is our heritage. Those days were cultural days, we used to perform our culture. Today it is all about money. In the past, we wanted to learn how to play a traditional instrument and I am wondering how it is going to be in the future, because the younger generations are not interested in playing the *danghaderi* or the *zhoma* as much as we were. They are more focused on modern life.

Analysis of the song *Hagu* (The dog)

The songs performed by the Dcaro group that I documented are strictly connected with the surrounding nature and the Kalahari environment. The musicians are very inspired by the place where they live and their way of life. The first song, *Bii* (The horse) «attempts to imitate the walk of the horse and it reflects on modern life. When we play this song, we ask ourselves: where are the hunters? Where are our husbands? Were they arrested? Because we are starving», as Qose Qarega said to me.

Hagu (The dog) is a song about the excitement of a dog expecting meat when it is tracking in hunting. The musicians imitate the bark of the animal throughout the song, too (Video 3). When hunting was not forbidden, dogs were very important tools for hunters, besides bows and arrows. In her book, Dorothea Frances Bleek wrote that «dogs were used by the Nharo to catch hares and small bucks for their larder, but never taken out to hunt larger game» (Bleek 1928: 16). It is significant to point out that both the tunes on the *dakateri* documented by Brearley (1984: 52) and the medicine dances documented by Alan Barnard among the Nharo in the 1970s were generally named after animal species: *Ngabe* (Giraffe), *Xama* (Impala), *Cko* (Gemsbok), etc. (Barnard 1979: 74).

The song *Hagu* can be divided into cycles of 6 elementary pulses, and the nine musicians play a very refined and structured interlocking game on the *danghaderi* with their thin wooden sticks (see Musical example 3). Xaga Tcuixgao (“XT” in the Musical example) inserts the metallic slider on the index of her left hand, changing the pitch of the string at every fifth elementary pulse of each cycle. The open string tuning is 65 Hz (C₂ -10 cents), the stopped string is 110 Hz (A₂). Just like in the *dakateri* “tunes” documented by Brearley (1984: 52), the distance between the two fundamentals is a major sixth (910 cents). Xaga Tcuixgao does not slide on the metallic string, she just places the slider in the proper position. Furthermore, she plays the pattern transcribed in the Musical example using the wooden stick held in her right hand. On her right, Qose Qarega (“QQ1” in the Musical example) conducts the group using her left hand while she plays a 5-stroke pattern in 12 (6 + 6) elementary pulses on the *danghaderi*. It is important to highlight that the third stroke played by Qose interlocks with the pattern played by Xaga Tcuixgao, while the following two strokes overlap Xaga’s pattern.

Proceeding to the right, Kgakgam Kaase (“KK” in the Musical example) strikes the string of the *danghaderi* every two elementary pulses, just like Tabaxae Kaase (“TK” in the Musical example). Namacgae Kaase (“NK” in the Musical example) is sitting down between Kgakgam and Tabaxae, and she slightly lifts up one side of the metallic dish with her left hand and releases it to the ground, changing the harmonic spectrum of the *danghaderi*. Furthermore, with the other hand, using a wooden stick she plays a 3-stroke pattern, whose second stroke interlocks with the pattern played by Kgakgam and Tabaxae.

Proceeding still to the right, Khamxlae Xgaiga (“KX” in the Musical example) claps her hands alternating two rhythmic patterns: one stroke every two elementary pulses (first pattern), and one stroke every three pulses (second pattern). Nconxae Xgaiga (“NX” in

the Musical example), in front of her, strikes the string of the instrument alternating the same two patterns played by Khamxlae. Qane Qate (“QQ2” in the Musical example) plays a 2-stroke pattern: one stroke at every change of note (first and fifth elementary pulse of the cycle). The ninth musician, Khoabaxae Thogo (“KT” in the Musical example) alternates three different rhythmic patterns that are also played by other musicians.

Unlike the tunes documented by Brearley in which the composite rhythm played by the three women was not «very intricate» (1984: 52), in the song *Hagu* performed by the Dcaro group we can experience a very complex and refined interlocking game played by the performers, as the Musical example 3 reveals. Furthermore, it is significant to point out that none of the musicians strike the string of the *danghaderi* on the second elementary pulse of each cycle, while the vocal part always starts exactly on the second elementary pulse, interlocking with all the rhythmic patterns played by the members of the Dcaro group on the instrument. The vocal part has not a melody, it is rather a “rhythmic game” played by some of the musicians sitting down in front of each other, imitating in unison the bark of the dog with the syllable “au”. Furthermore, Namacgae Kaase lifts up one side of the metallic dish with her left hand, changing the harmonic spectrum of the *danghaderi*, on the second and fifth elementary pulses of each cycle, following the vocal part.

Final remarks

D’kar is a village where group and individual musical practices are still very active and dynamic among Nharo speaking people. For the musicians observed in this article, music is a precious way to feel the vibrations of a lost past where life was flowing in a very different way. As Kaufman Shelemay (2006) and Sloboda (1985), among others, have asserted, music has a peculiar capability to activate mental processes recovering memories of all kinds, recreating the images of specific events and emotions experienced in the past. For many of these music makers, life today is hard in comparison with the past when they lived in the bush; feelings of alienation and frustration fill their hearts and music operates as a special natural medicine for their souls. Such sad feelings are also expressed by both Xhara Qoma and Xhoxhae Xhukuri in the lyrics of their songs *Koli* and *Xgoe*.

Furthermore, it is important to highlight that in the past the musicians observed in this paper played their instruments only for the sake of self-entertainment or at specific everyday life occasions (i.e. the *danghaderi* to bring good luck to the hunters), while today, they play to make a living and they also perform at “presentational” events (Turino 2008), such as traditional festivals and at tourists lodges. So, they have moved from a status of non-professional to semi-professional musicians, or even professional in some cases. That is why music has a different meaning and role in their lives today in comparison with the past, and for all these reasons, we can consider their music as “resettled” musical practices.

The Khoisan younger generations in D’kar have not experienced life in the bush, so the instruments analysed in this article do not really receive their attention, because they are

mainly interested in hip-hop and afrobeat from South Africa or Botswana itself, just like my informant and interpreter Alfred Cg'ase Tshumu, born in 1991, who is also an afrobeat producer. The *zhoma* and the *danghaderi* belong to a very different way of life, while the younger generations have to deal with the problems of a society where their parents are considered "outsiders", and they hardly find a place in the "new life". The music played by Xhara Qoma, Xhoxhae Xhukuri and Dcaro group is an endangered cultural activity, it belongs to an older generation even if some young women are approaching the *danghaderi* (Video 3), and Xhoxhae's children are learning to play the *zhoma*. It is my intention to continue documenting the musical practices in D'kar Village in order to observe the future developments.

Appendix

About Khoisan languages and orthography

Khoisan languages are characterised by the heavy use of the so-called "click consonants" and are divided in three main groups: Khoe-Kwadi, Kx'a and Tuu languages. Nharo (or Naro) is a dialect of the Tshu-Kwe, a Khoe-Kwadi language spoken in eastern Namibia and in the Ghanzi District of Botswana, where D'kar (or Dekar) Village is situated. The !Kung language belongs to the Kx'a group and is mainly spoken in Namibia, while Taa and Kwi are the two main languages spoken by the Tuu group (Treis 1988). Although click consonants are very rare cross-linguistically, but they can be found also in some Bantu languages in southeast Africa (Xhosa, Zulu, Swati and Phuthi) and southwest Africa (Yeyi, Fwe, Mbukushu, Manyo and Kwangali). This is one of the results of the culture contact between Khoisan hunter-gatherers and Bantu pastoralists; the latter accomplished their expansion from central Africa approx. 5,000 years ago and reached southern Africa approx. 3,000 years later (Phillipson 1977, Pakendorf *et al.*, 2017).

Clicks are consonant sounds produced by allowing air to pass into (rather than out of) the mouth. The spelling and writing of these clicks often caused problems for both scholars and readers. The Egyptologist Karl Richard Lepsius created in 1854 a system of symbols to put the clicks into writing (1863), in 1856 it was adopted by the Rhenish Mission Society (RMS) and became the standard Khoisan system (Barnard 1992). Nharo language makes use of four click consonants which can be written using the following symbols of the standard Khoisan system:

/	A dental produced by sucking the tip of the tongue on the teeth.
≠	An alveolar produced by pulling the blade of the tongue quickly away from the alveolar ridge, immediately behind the teeth.
//	A lateral affricate produced by placing the tip of the tongue on the roof of the mouth and releasing air on one side of the mouth, between the side of the tongue and the cheek.
!	A palatal produced by pulling the tip of the tongue quickly away from the front of the hard palate.

In the early 1990s, Hessel Visser, a Dutch missionary and linguist who lived in D'kar, worked on a Nharo orthography and dictionary (2001) and a Nharo translation of the Bible was published in 1994 (Guenther 1999). In this article, I have used Visser's orthography, since the musicians of D'kar use this orthography and not the standard Khoisan symbols to write their names. In the table below is shown the correspondences between the two systems:

Standard Khoisan system	Hessel Visser's orthography
/	c
≠	tc
//	x
!	q

Multimedia Contents

Videos

The three videos accompanying this article were shot during my second year of fieldwork in Botswana, more precisely on 12th July 2019 in D'kar Village were the Nharo music makers live. I used a Panasonic HC-V770 video camera (FULL HD) with a Røde Stereo Video Mic.

1. [Koli \[4:12\]](#). Fieldwork: D'kar Village (Botswana), 12th July 2019. Performer: Xhara Qoma (guitar). Research and shootings: Alessandro Cosentino.
2. [Xgoe \[14:42\]](#). Fieldwork: D'kar Village (Botswana), 12th July 2019. Performer: Xhoxhae Xhukuri (*zhoma*). Research and shootings: Alessandro Cosentino.
3. [Hagu \(The dog\) \[4:02\]](#). Fieldwork: D'kar Village (Botswana), 12th July 2019. Performer: Dcaro group (*danghaderi*). Research and shootings: Alessandro Cosentino.

Multimedia contents are also available via
QR Code

Musical example 1. *Koli* by Xhara Qoma.

Elementary pulses: 212 M.M.

The musical score is presented in three systems, each with a vocal line and a guitar line. The time signature is 12/8. The lyrics are as follows:

System 1:
 Voice: Ye i - ye u - we iye u - u - we
 Guitar: (Chords and rhythmic markings)

System 2:
 V.: e - e kha - sa koe nxae koe
 G.: (Chords and rhythmic markings)

System 3:
 V.: nxae ghe oh eh ih
 G.: (Chords and rhythmic markings)

Rhythmic markings include downward-pointing triangles (▼) and upward-pointing triangles (▲) placed below the notes, indicating specific pulse patterns.

Musical example 2. Xgoe by Xhoxhae Xhukuri.

Elementary pulses: 314 M.M.

The musical score is presented in four systems, each with a vocal line and a Z. line. The time signature is 12. The notes are represented by black dots on a five-line staff, with flat symbols (b) indicating specific pitches. The lyrics are written below the notes.

System 1:

- Voice:** 12. Notes: b4, b4, b4, b4. Lyrics: A - iye iye a - iye
- Zhoma:** 12. Notes: b4, b4, b4, b4, b4, b4, b4, b4.

System 2:

- V.:** 12. Notes: b4, b4, b4, b4. Lyrics: Tii ra cui - i
- Z.:** 12. Notes: b4, b4, b4, b4, b4, b4, b4, b4.

System 3:

- V.:** 12. Notes: b4, b4, b4, b4, b4, b4. Lyrics: ra - a a - re - sa e
- Z.:** 12. Notes: b4, b4, b4, b4, b4, b4, b4, b4.

"RESETTLED" MUSICAL PRACTICES

V. 12

mh

Z. 12

V. 12

Khoe tu - ue khoe tu - ue

Z. 12

V. 12

Tii ra cgo - ma

Z. 12

COSENTINO

V. 12

ra - a a - re sa e

Z. 12

V. 12

mh

Z. 12

Musical example 3. *Hagu* by Dcaro group.

Elementary pulses: 366 M.M.

The image displays a musical score for the piece "Hagu" by the Dcaro group. The score is organized into ten staves, each representing a different instrument or voice part. The parts are labeled on the left as Voice, XT, QQ1, KK, NK, TK, KX, NX, QQ2, and KT. Each staff begins with a treble clef and a time signature of 6/8. The Voice part includes vocalizations "Au" and "au" under specific notes. The KX part is characterized by a series of 'x' marks on the staff. The other parts (XT, QQ1, KK, NK, TK, NX, QQ2, KT) feature rhythmic patterns of notes and rests. The score is titled "Elementary pulses: 366 M.M." at the top.

COSENTINO

The image displays a musical score for the piece "COSENTINO". It consists of ten staves, each labeled with a letter code on the left: V, XT, QQ1, KK, NK, TK, KX, NX, QQ2, and KT. Each staff begins with a treble clef and a time signature of 6. The V staff contains three 'x' marks above the first three measures, with the syllables "au", "au", and "qu" written below them. The XT, QQ1, KK, NK, TK, NX, QQ2, and KT staves contain a series of notes (dots) on the staff lines, with some notes appearing in pairs. The KX staff contains four 'x' marks above the first four measures. The overall layout is a vertical sequence of staves.

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